

Neurological Aspect of Drowning

Wayan Widyantara*, M. Sofyan Faridi*, I Gusti Agung Gede Ariswanda* and I Putu Eka Widyadharma*,¹

*Department of Neurology, Faculty of Medicine, Udayana University, Sanglah General Hospital, Bali, Indonesia.

ABSTRACT Drowning is an event of submersion or immersion in liquid which results in respiratory impairment. In 1970, drowning was the third leading cause of accidental death in the U.S., resulting in 7,860 deaths in the U.S. alone and roughly 15,000 mortality worldwide. When someone is in a drowning process, there is a limit in which he can't longer hold their airway clear. Eventually, water will pour into the mouth, which will be either spat out or swallowed. Initial resuscitation involves placing the victim in a supine position with trunk and head at the same level. If the victim still actively breathe in the absence of consciousness, they should place in a lateral decubitus position. The cardiopulmonary rescue should be initiation immediately. Clinical outcomes depend on the early onset of resuscitation.

KEYWORDS drowning, immersion, swallowed, airway, resuscitation

Introduction

This definition is devised in 2002 by The Brain Resuscitation Task Force who met during World Congress on Drowning, due to varying drowning definitions [1]. Drowning is a simple definition. Turns out to be the third leading cause of accidental death worldwide with 7% of all injury-related deaths, while coming up at second under the same issue among children aged 1 to 14 years in the U.S.

Epidemiology

In 1970, drowning was the third leading cause of accidental death in the U.S., resulting in 7,860 deaths in the U.S. alone and roughly 15,000 mortality worldwide [2]. Perspective, 80,000 persons have had drowning but survive yearly, with 6,000 died from it. Thus it can be concluded that approximately one from 13 persons died due to drowning. Among them, almost half were young (i.e. less than 20 years old). A more recent epidemiological data had shown that drowning became the leading cause of death in 5 to 14 years age group. An epidemiological study patient's in Turkey had median pediatric age of drowning was

4.2 years with toddlers (0-4 years old) by almost 70% [3]. Perhaps a more representative drowning incidence can be obtained by data from Thailand, which demonstrated 107 per 100,000 2-year old children [3].

Definition

In 2002, the Brain Resuscitation Task Force who met at World Congress on Drowning had established a consensus expert regarding the definition of drowning. It stated that "drowning is the process of experiencing respiratory impairment from submersion/immersion in liquid" the description points to a process rather than a "staccato" definition [1]. It implicates to the following explanation, i.e. if the victim rescued, it is defined as non-fatal drowning. If, however, the victim dies at any time as a consequence of drowning, then it is termed as fatal drowning. Furthermore, the consensus expert also abolished non-specific terms such as "near-drowning, dry/wet drowning, secondary drowning, or active/passive drowning".

Pathophysiology

When someone is in a drowning process, there is a limit in which he or she can no longer hold their airway clear. Eventually, water will pour into the mouth, which will be either spat out or swallowed. The victim will then try their best to hold their breath. However, in the end, they will no longer be able to resist their respiratory drive. When they finally attempt to inhale, some water will spill into the respiratory tract and triggers a cough and laryngospasm. Although briefly, due to the release mechanism as a consequence of brain hypoxia. When the operation of

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DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.Neurological-Aspect-Drowning

First Received: September 20, 2019

Accepted: October 04, 2019

Editor-in-chief: Ivan Inkov (BG)

¹Department of Neurology, Faculty of Medicine, Udayana University, Sanglah General Hospital, Bali, Indonesia.; Email: eka.widyadharma@unud.ac.id

Figure 1: Resuscitation algorithm for drowning scenario, adapted from https://www.nejm.org/doi/10.1056/NEJMra1013317?url_ver=Z39.88-2003&rfr_id=ori:rid:crossref.org&rfr_dat=cr_pub%3dwww.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov.

drowning is uninterrupted, water will continue to pour in, and hypoxia leads to loss of consciousness, apnea, and cardiac arrest [4]. The whole process of drowning occurs briefly, lasting from seconds to minutes. The ultimate results of aspirated water into the lungs can be grave. Consequently leads to water-induced alveoli dysfunction (pulmonary oedema), surfactant loss, and increased alveolar-capillary membrane permeability. All result in decreased lung compliance improved of areas with very low or zero ventilation to perfusion in the lungs, atelectasis, as well as bronchospasm.

Drowning also has a profound effect on a victim's brain. Hypoxia consequently leads to hypoxic or anoxic and ischemic brain injury (so-called hypoxic/anoxic injuries/HAI). Brain cells can only survive about 4 minutes in the absence or reduced oxygen supply (i.e. cerebral anoxia and hypoxia, respectively). Furthermore, hypoxia means reduced oxygen supply despite adequate blood perfusion into organs. When HAI occurs, it is responsible for the loss of consciousness during drowning and the latter neurologic sequelae in drowning survivors. There are several areas of the brain more susceptible to ischemic injury, which comprises vascular end zones, hippocampus, insular cortex, and basal ganglia. The relationship is linear as the more

severe hypoxic-ischemia is, the more extensive and widespread brain injury will occur [5].

Diagnosis

Neurological impacts confirmed by the history of drowning and neurological manifestations that follow. Drowning survivor can suffer from ataxia, dysarthria, and tetraplegia [6]. In fact, the most common findings in severe cases of drowning-induced HAI consist of a combination of memory and motor deficits with variable executive impairment [7] and other less common deficits including semantic verbal fluency, short- and long-term verbal memory (free and cued recall), and verbal learning when compared with the respiratory failure-induced HAI cases [8]. In children victims, neurological impairments were reported as motor deficits such as impaired excellent motor skills as well as memory and executive deficits, albeit rarely [9].

A study compared the structural and functional MRI and neuropsychological outcomes of chronic survivors compared with healthy controls. The study found no difference between the survivor and control group in terms of neuropsychological assessments and structural MRI. However, fMRI demonstrated increased brain response in the motor (left putamen and in-

sula), and memory (left cuneus and lingual gyrus) tasks among survivors. The investigators concluded that the resulting functional brain changes in motor and visual regions might indicate reduced brain reserve in the absence of structural and neurobehavioral alterations. Furthermore, when the drowning survivors have given the motor task, the left putamen is activated more vividly when compared with controls. It means these areas may be responsible for adaptation in classic areas recruitment from the motor area network. The putamen is more activated as a function of motor performance in the ageing population, in line with the observed performance decline seen among the drowning survivors [10].

Management

Initial resuscitation involves placing the victim in a supine position with trunk and head at the same level. If the victim still actively breathe in the absence of consciousness, they should place in a lateral decubitus position. Cardio-lung resuscitation should initiated immediately. It's known that drowning can result in gasping or apnea while the heart is still beating. In this case, ventilation without chest compression is adequate for resuscitation. Besides, cardiac arrest, when it occurs in drowning victims, tend to be due to lack of oxygen supply. Therefore, a CPR with ABC relative to CAB sequence recommended. The European Resuscitation Council recommends five initial rescue breaths instead of two. The initial ventilation is more difficult to achieve as water trapped within the alveoli hampers gas diffusion. The most drowning victims are young; there is a considerably higher chance of successful CPR than other cardiac arrest cases (e.g. heart attack).

Subsequently, the victim should be handled appropriately by advanced-life-support teams. Drowning classifying the victims into six different types of triage, in which each scenario will be treated differently, tailored to their needs and survival prediction (figure 1)[11].

Administration of high oxygen flow (up to 15 litres per minute) tolerated in acute settings — the oxygen saturation targeted between 92% and 96%. Circulation should be secured by intravenous crystalloid infusion whenever the victim shows hemodynamic compromise, regardless of the drowning (fresh or saltwater). Follow-up care usually conducted in the ICU where victims will treat according to the ARDS protocol. It's known that drowning victims recover faster and better than patients with ARDS due to other causes. Weaning from mechanical ventilation can be initiated after 24 hours. One significant pulmonary complication to be addressed is pneumonia, albeit only 12% of patients of drowning victims will eventually need antibiotic therapies for it [11]. From a neurological perspective, when a CPR performed, there is a similar risk of neurologic damage. In this case, therapeutic hypothermia can exert protective effects. Hypothermia reduces the brain's oxygen consumption, delaying cellular anoxia, and ATP depletion in a temperature-dependent fashion. It's known that the rate of brain oxygen consumption is reduced by roughly 5% with each 1°C of temperature decline within the range of 37°C to 20°C [12]

Prognosis

The prognosis following drowning varies depending on the array of factors. Among the pediatric group, 52 out of 54 fresh-water drowning victims with a mean estimated submersion time of 3.7 minutes were completely normal. It's reporting that good

survivors had a higher IQ than the general population, and this perhaps was related to superior visuomotor (performance skills) and better survival. However, permanent brain damage can be more common than expected, as approximately 10% of survivors suffer from severe neurologic complications [10]. Clinical outcomes depend on the early onset of resuscitation.

Competing interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding

The author fully funds the cost of this research.

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